

Heart failure disease progression assessment in patients through the use of traditional machine learning approaches

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Abstract. Heart Failure (HF), characterized by the heart's inability to pump a sufficient amount, represents one of the major global health challenges. The diagnosis of HF relies on a combination of clinical assessments and biomarkers derived from various diagnostic tools and data sources. These biomarkers, including those from blood tests and physical examinations, are crucial for identifying patients at risk of developing HF. Accurate identification of individuals at risk of developing HF is essential for timely intervention and management, which can help slow disease progression and significantly improve patient outcomes. In this paper, we present a methodology for classifying patients into three distinct categories: (1) those who have HF at the baseline appointment, (2) those who will develop HF within the next five years, and (3) those who will develop HF within the next ten years. The dataset used in this paper consists of blood biomarkers and physical examination data. After applying several machine learning models, we found that the ensemble model gradient boosting decision tree (GBDT) achieved the best results. After performing 5-fold cross-validation, the accuracy was 0.95, and the F1-score was 0.94. We have also extracted key features that are strongly associated with patient outcomes, such as NYHA class, CK-MB, total cholesterol, BMI, heart rate, diastolic pressure, creatinine, and NT-proBNP. Additionally, we used SHAP and LIME to improve the model's interpretability, as explainable machine learning models are easier to implement in real clinical practice. By using these methods, we enhanced the transparency of the model, allowing clinicians to better understand the predictions and make more informed decisions.

Keywords: heart failure, gradient boosting decision tree, ensemble model, classification.

1 Introduction

Heart failure (HF) is a complex clinical syndrome resulting from structural or functional cardiac abnormalities that impair the heart's ability to fill or eject blood [1]. As a result, the heart cannot meet the metabolic and circulatory demands of the body. Clinically, HF manifests through symptoms such as breathlessness, fatigue, and ankle swelling, often accompanied by elevated jugular venous pressure, pulmonary crackles, or peripheral edema [1]. It represents one of the leading causes of hospitalization among older adults and is associated with substantial morbidity and mortality. According to the European Society of Cardiology, approximately 26 million people worldwide live with HF, with an additional 3.6 million newly diagnosed each year [2]. Mortality remains high, with 17–45% of patients dying within the first year after diagnosis, and most others within five years [2]. Beyond its clinical burden, HF is also one of the most expensive chronic conditions to manage in high-income countries. The need for repeated diagnostic evaluations, invasive procedures, therapeutic adjustments, and frequent hospital readmissions contributes to healthcare expenditures reaching 1–2% of total national healthcare budgets [2]. At the same time, these extensive diagnostic and monitoring activities generate large, heterogeneous datasets stored in registries and institutional databases, providing an opportunity to study disease progression, optimize management, and improve risk prediction [3].

The diagnosis of HF relies on an approach that integrates symptoms, physical examination, and objective markers of cardiac dysfunction. Echocardiography remains the cornerstone of confirming HF, as it provides essential information on ventricular systolic and diastolic function, chamber size, valve abnormalities, and pulmonary pressures. However, in many non-acute or resource limited settings, echocardiography may not be available at the time of patient presentation. In such situations, measuring natriuretic peptides (BNP or NT-proBNP) serves as an effective initial diagnostic step, primarily due to their high negative predictive value [1].

Natriuretic peptides directly reflect increased intracardiac pressures, myocardial wall stress, and neurohumoral activation. In addition to natriuretic peptides, biochemical indicators of renal function (creatinine, urea), electrolyte balance (sodium, potassium), and metabolic status (glucose), together with markers of inflammation and organ injury (CRP, AST, ALT, bilirubin), provide essential information about comorbid conditions that significantly influence disease progression and prognosis [4]. Hematological parameters including hemoglobin, hematocrit, MCV, MCH, and RDW are increasingly recognized as important indicators of systemic alterations associated with HF [4, 5].

Also, physical examination remains crucial for detecting hemodynamic disturbances and early manifestations of decompensation. Clinical parameters such as blood pressure, heart rate, the presence of gallop rhythms or murmurs, elevated jugular venous pressure, pulmonary crackles, and peripheral edema form the foundation of the initial bedside assessment. The New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional classification continues to serve as a widely used measure of symptom severity and correlates strongly with mortality and rehospitalization risk [6]. Additionally, body

mass index (BMI) and the presence of bilateral edema offer insight into volume status, nutritional state, and fluid retention.

When combined, biomarkers and physical examination findings provide a comprehensive view of the underlying pathophysiology of HF, enable more accurate risk stratification, and support the differentiation of HF from other causes of dyspnea or fluid overload. These parameters are not only clinically meaningful but also highly suitable for machine learning (ML) applications because they are standardized, routinely collected, and widely available across healthcare centers. They offer a foundation for developing models for early detection, classification, and long-term prediction of heart failure progression [5].

Recent studies demonstrate that ML algorithms can predict HF with high accuracy and often outperform traditional approaches. Traditional statistical modeling often fails to capture the nonlinear and high-dimensional relationships that characterize HF pathophysiology, while ML methods can extract subtle patterns that improve diagnostic and prognostic performance. Across recent studies, supervised learning algorithms such as logistic regression, random forests, gradient boosting methods (XGBoost, LightGBM), support vector machines (SVM), and deep neural networks (DNN) have demonstrated strong predictive capabilities.

Ensemble methods, especially random forests and gradient boosting consistently achieve state-of-the-art performance due to their robustness to noisy clinical variables, ability to model nonlinear interactions, and built-in feature importance estimation. For example, Adler et al. demonstrate that model based on boosted decision tree applied to hematology and biochemistry data can predict HF with accuracy comparable to natriuretic peptides, underscoring the diagnostic value of blood-based biomarkers [7]. Similarly, James et al. showed that HF can be reliably predicted from full blood count and biochemical parameters, achieving high AUROC values and identifying hematological markers, such as RDW, hemoglobin, and hematocrit as key contributors to model performance [5]. Further, Pu et al. constructed multiple ML models using routine blood test parameters, demonstrating that the random forest model achieved the highest accuracy when identifying individuals at risk for HF (AUC up to 0.945 in validation) [8]. White blood cell count, neutrophils, red blood cells, hemoglobin, platelets, and monocyte-to-lymphocyte ratio were identified as key predictors. Importantly, the use of explainable ML framework such as SHAP has improved model transparency by clarifying feature contributions [8]. Miyashita et al. extended this line of research by applying a novel approach (LAMP) to large datasets, identifying hundreds of clinically meaningful combinations of clinical, physiological, and laboratory variables that predict incident HF years before its onset, demonstrating that ML can uncover complex interactions not captured by traditional statistical models [9]. Although Chicco and Jurman reported excellent survival-prediction performance using only serum creatinine and ejection fraction, their approach relies on echocardiography derived ejection fraction, which limits applicability in settings where imaging is not available, further highlighting the value of models based only on routinely accessible laboratory and clinical features [10].

Beyond early diagnosis and risk-stratification, recent studies have also applied ML to broader aspects of HF management and long-term prediction. Segar et al.

developed and validated ML models for estimating 10-year risk of incident HF in the general population, demonstrating that gradient boosting and random forest algorithms outperform traditional risk scores and effectively integrate demographic, clinical, laboratory, and ECG-derived features [11]. Nguyen et al. further emphasized the prognostic value of temporal clinical data, showing that incorporating longitudinal measurements of biomarkers and vital signs leads to substantially improved prediction of cardiovascular outcomes compared with models relying only on baseline values [12]. A recent study on prediction of chronic HF progression highlighted the capacity of ensemble models to identify patients at increased risk of deterioration based on routinely collected clinical parameters, including renal function markers, natriuretic peptides, and cardiometabolic variables [13].

Despite this broad progress, existing studies mostly address HF diagnosis, onset prediction, survival modeling and rehospitalization risk. In contrast, fewer works investigate long-term prediction of HF development and patient stratification over multi-year intervals using only routine biomarkers and physical examination findings. This gap highlights the need for practical, accessible models capable of identifying individuals who may develop HF during the clinically relevant time periods such as five or ten years.

2 Materials and methods

The idea of this paper is to develop a ML methodology capable of classifying patients into three clinically relevant classes: individuals with HF already present at the baseline assessment, individuals who are likely to develop HF within five years and individuals who are expected to develop HF within ten years. The analysis is based on demographic information, blood biomarkers and physical examination findings, making the proposed approach practical for settings where diagnostic imaging cannot be immediately accessible. In the following, dataset is described, along with the preprocessing steps and ML algorithms employed to construct and evaluate the models.

2.1 Dataset

Clinical data were obtained from the Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases of Vojvodina, comprising a cohort of 282 adult patients with different parameters. The dataset included demographic data, physical examination findings and blood biomarkers. All patient records were anonymized prior to analysis.

Clinical assessments were available at two earlier examination points and at a final follow-up visit, enabling the construction of a longitudinal database suitable for modeling HF development over time.

For each patient, demographic information such as age and gender was recorded at baseline. Physical examination parameters included body mass index (BMI), systolic and diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, NYHA class, and the presence of characteristic cardiac findings such as mitral insufficiency murmurs, carotid murmurs, and bilateral peripheral edema. Laboratory biomarkers included hematological

measures (leukocyte count, erythrocyte count, hemoglobin, MCV, MCH, MCHC, and platelets), markers of renal function (creatinine and urea), metabolic indicators (glucose, uric acid, lipid profile), liver enzymes (AST, ALT, bilirubin), cardiac biomarkers (CK-MB, troponin, and NT-proBNP), electrolytes such as sodium and potassium and inflammatory markers such as CRP. The described dataset is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Dataset overview.

Based on clinical diagnoses documented across timepoints, patients were categorized into three outcome classes that describe the temporal pattern of HF development: those with heart failure already present at baseline, those who developed heart failure within five years, and those who developed heart failure within ten years. This multiclass target served as the primary outcome for ML classification.

2.2 Machine learning models

Prior to modeling, all identifier fields and non-numeric variables were removed. Missing values in continuous variables were imputed using the k-nearest neighbors algorithm ($k = 7$), which uses similarity between patients to estimate feasible replacement values while preserving the local structure of the clinical data space. Continuous predictors were standardized to have zero mean and unit variance to ensure numerical stability during training and to prevent variable scale from influencing model performance.

After the preprocessing step, several supervised ML algorithms were evaluated, including logistic regression, SVM, decision trees, random forests, and gradient boosting decision trees (GBDT). After evaluation, GBDT demonstrated the strongest and most stable performance and it was selected as the final model. Model performance was assessed using 5-fold cross-validation, and metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were computed. Proposed methodology has been implemented in Python 3.7.6, Spyder environment 4.1, using CPU Intel Core i5.

To better understand how individual clinical features contributed to the model’s decision-making process, feature importance scores were extracted from the trained GBDT classifier. This approach identifies variables that contribute most to reducing classification error across all decision trees, highlighting clinically meaningful predictors of long-term HF development.

3 Results and discussion

During the evaluation process, the GBDT classification model consistently demonstrated the highest performance. The performance of the proposed GBDT model was evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation to ensure its robustness and generalizability. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 0.95 and F1-score of 0.94. The model showed high performance in identifying patients without HF, achieving a precision of 0.94, a recall of 0.97, and an F1-score of 0.96. The class representing patients who will develop HF within the next five years exhibited perfect precision of 1.00 but a slightly lower recall (0.89), suggesting that while false positives were minimized, a small proportion of true cases may not have been detected. Patients predicted to develop HF within ten years were classified with balanced performance, reflected in precision and recall values of 0.92 and an overall F1-score of 0.92. Table 1 summarizes the precision, recall, and F1-scores obtained on the test data for each class.

Table 1. Precision, recall and F1-scores obtained on the test data.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
No HF	0.94	0.97	0.96
HF in next five years	1.00	0.89	0.94
HF in next ten years	0.92	0.92	0.92
Average:	0.96	0.93	0.94

These findings are further illustrated by the confusion matrix shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix for the test set.

The average performance across all classes further demonstrates the model's stability, with a mean precision of 0.96, mean recall of 0.93, and mean F1-score of 0.94.

Additionally, the top ten most influential features extracted from GBDT are shown in Fig. 3. and their relevance aligns closely with established pathophysiological mechanisms underlying HF.

Fig. 3. Ten features that have the highest importance score.

The NYHA functional class emerged as the strongest predictor, reflecting its role as a direct clinical descriptor of symptom severity and functional limitation. Patients

with higher NYHA classes demonstrate more pronounced dyspnea, reduced exercise tolerance, and hemodynamic compromise, making this variable a powerful indicator of existing or impending heart failure. BMI was the second most important feature. Elevated BMI is associated with metabolic dysregulation, fluid retention, and an increased likelihood of developing HFpEF, a phenotype commonly linked with obesity and systemic inflammation.

Among vital signs, resting heart rate and diastolic blood pressure contributed substantially to model performance. A persistently elevated heart rate may indicate compensatory sympathetic activation in response to reduced cardiac output, while lower diastolic pressure can reflect impaired stroke volume and diminished peripheral perfusion, both hallmark features of progressive cardiac dysfunction.

Serum biomarkers also played a central role in prediction. Sodium levels contributed meaningfully, as hyponatremia is frequently observed in advanced heart failure and is closely linked to neurohormonal activation and adverse outcomes. Glucose levels, representing metabolic status, were also important; hyperglycemia and diabetes mellitus significantly accelerate structural and functional cardiac deterioration. Creatinine reflects the well-established interaction between cardiac and renal impairment, known as the cardiorenal syndrome.

Markers of systemic and organ-specific stress were also relevant. AST emerged as an important predictor due to its association with hepatic congestion secondary to right-sided heart failure or systemic venous pressure overload. MCH frequently reflects anemia which is common comorbidity in chronic heart failure that contributes to reduced oxygen delivery and worsening fatigue.

Finally, NT-proBNP, a gold-standard biomarker of myocardial wall stress and volume overload, was appropriately identified as one of the key contributors to the model, reinforcing the robustness of the feature selection process.

We have also used SHAP and LIME values to improve the interpretability of the model and to better understand the contribution of individual features to the predicted HF risk. SHAP values highlighted the most influential biomarkers across the entire cohort, including NYHA class, CK-MB, creatinine, and NT-proBNP. In addition to this, LIME local explanations demonstrated that, for a representative patient classified into the class “HF in 5 years”, the strongest contributors to the predicted risk were NYHA class and bilateral peripheral oedema, followed by biomarker measurements such as uric acid and BMI. This confirms that the model’s decision aligns with clinically relevant HF indicators.

Together, these findings demonstrate that the GBDT model not only captures known clinical determinants of HF but also effectively integrates multidimensional physiological information.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we developed a ML model capable of predicting long-term HF development using only routinely collected clinical variables, including blood biomarkers and physical examination findings. By classifying patients into three classes, those

with existing HF, those who will develop the condition within five years and those who will develop it within ten years, the proposed approach enables early identification of individuals at risk. Among several evaluated models, the GBDT classification model demonstrated the best performance, achieving an accuracy of 0.95 and F1-score of 0.94, with consistently high precision and recall for all classes. The results show that routinely available and low-cost clinical measurements contain substantial predictive information for estimating long-term HF risk. Key contributing features, such as NYHA class, BMI, heart rate, diastolic blood pressure, sodium, creatinine, NT-proBNP, and other laboratory biomarkers, align with established pathophysiological mechanisms, further validating the clinical relevance of the model.

Future work should explore the integration of additional modalities, such as longitudinal biomarker trends, echocardiography features, as well as external validation on larger and more diverse populations. However, the present study demonstrates that a practical, interpretable, and widely applicable ML model can be developed using data routinely encountered in everyday clinical practice, offering a promising step toward improved early detection and long-term monitoring of HF risk.

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